

Near-infrared spectroscopy as a green technology for more sustainable analyses on intact olive and olive oil

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The olive oil industry is a significant productive sector in the European Union, and the related production process is characterized by practices and techniques associated with several adverse effects on the environment. Conventional ripeness analyses on olives, and quality analyses on olive oils, require different analytical tools, chemicals, sample preparation, and are time consuming. Nowadays, the nondestructive optical method based on visible/near-infrared (vis/NIR) spectroscopy, representing a simple, rapid, and easy-to-use method to predict olive and olive oil quality parameters (Salguero-Chaparro et al., 2013; Marquez et al., 2005), could be the solution to reduce solvents and energy consumption in-laboratory. The aim of the work is to evaluate the environmental impact of the use of optical vis/NIR technologies for analytical assessment in comparison to chemical analyses performed on olives and olive oils. Applying the life cycle assessment method, the functional unit was identified in the analysis service provided by the laboratory. An approach “from cradle to grave” considered all the inputs and outputs of each analysis, enclosing machineries, reagents, and energy necessary for analyses. Results showed that the hotspots for chemical analyses are identified in the energy required from the machineries and in the chemicals used; while for the optical, calibration activities are mainly responsible for the impacts. A comparison between impacts of chemical and optical methods performed on olives showed an average gap of 15 times. The same comparison performed between olive oils analyses identified a gap equal to 36 times. These gaps can increase, considering a higher number of samples analysed during the life cycle of the vis/NIR device and/or implementing predictive models capable of estimating a wider number of parameters simultaneously. Overall, quantifying the environmental damage, results showed clear advantages for optical analysis, defining spectroscopy as a green technology.

Keywords: spectrophotometer, LCA, quality control, nondestructive analysis, optical

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